

Tlc Separation of some Synthetic Dyes on Silica Gel Layers impregnated with Nickel(II) Ion

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LITERATURE¹ reveals that the separation of dyes is difficult because of spots tailing and close hR_f values on untreated silica thin layers. The impregnation of the adsorbent layers in tlc has resulted into a better and effective resolution of a variety of compounds^{2,3}. However, only a few reports⁴ are available on the separation of dyes on impregnated thin layers. We have therefore undertaken the separation of some twelve dyes on metal salts impregnated layers. Among the various salts tried nickel chloride impregnation improved the tlc separation of dyes.

Experimental

The dyes used were indigo carmine, orange G, naphthol yellow, malachite green, gentian violet and benzopurpurin 4B (all from BDH), auramine O and rhodamine B (both Fluka), fluorescein sodium (May and Baker), thymol blue (Loba-Chemie) and eosin blue (E. Merck). Silica gel G (10–40 μ) with calcium sulphate (13%) as binder and impurities of chloride, iron and lead (with 0.02% each) showing a pH of 7.0 in 10% aqueous suspension, was used. Other reagents and chemicals used were from BDH and Polypharm.

Thin layer plates (20 cm \times 20 cm \times 0.5 mm) were prepared by spreading a slurry of silica gel in distilled water. For impregnated plates, slurry was prepared in distilled water containing varying amounts of different metal salts. The solutions of dyes ($10^{-3} M$) were prepared in ethanol-water (4 : 1, v/v) and applied to the plates at 500 ng level. The chromatograms were developed upto 15 cm for 50 min, which had been pre-equilibrated with mobile phase for 10–15 min at $25 \pm 2^\circ$. The plates were dried in an oven at 60° . Since the dyes are self-visualised compounds hence the spots were located as such.

Results and Discussion

To find out a suitable impregnating agent, various metal salts in different concentrations were tried, namely Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and Ni^{II} . It was found that 1.5% $NiCl_2$ impregnation gave better results, and various compositions of mobile phases of different polarity were tried to select a best mobile phase. Acetone-acetic acid-benzene (9 : 6 : 6, by vol) gave the compact and well-resolved spots and the hR_f values for the dyes were recorded.

The hR_f values of dyes on plain and 1.5% $NiCl_2$ impregnated layers are recorded in Table 1. It is

important to mention that on plain silica gel plates most of the dyes showed tailing. It is apparent from Table 1 that only six dyes were separated from a twelve-component mixture on plain silica plates while eight dyes were clearly separated on 1.5% NiCl₂ impregnated silica gel layers. The present chromatographic system has been found better than the reported systems⁴ because of compact spots, better resolution and lower hR_f values (solvent front = 15 cm). The resolution of the dyes was verified by calculating resolution possibilities. The resolution data was calculated by the usual method³. The standard deviations calculated were between 0.45 to 0.50 which reveals a better reproducibility.

TABLE 1— hR_f VALUES OF DYES ON PLAIN AND IMPREGNATED SILICA GEL LAYERS

	Plain	NiCl ₂ -impregnated (1.5%)
Indigo carmine	00	00
Rhodamine B	78	99
Naphthol yellow	06	66
Auramin O	36	80
Orange G	02	09
Malachite green	48 ^a	78
Fluorescein sodium	98 ^a	96
Thymol blue	94 ^a	89
Eosin blue	98 ^a	100
Benzopurpurin 4B	10	00
Methylene blue	04	09
Gentian violet	69 ^a	80

^a Tailing.

The impregnating agent chosen was from transition metal series which has a great tendency of complex formation with suitable ligands and dyes. Therefore, the better resolution on impregnated plates may be due to the partition of metal-dye complexes formed on Ni^{II} impregnated layer rather than pure dyes resulting into better separation of dyes. This was verified by preparing the complexes of these dyes with Ni^{II} and the separating them on plain silica gel plates using the same mobile. The hR_f values for this system were in very good agreement with those found on impregnated layers for pure dyes.

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